

Neutrosophic Overlap Function and Its Derived Neutrosophic Residual Implication

Xingna Zhang¹, Qingqing Hu² and Xiaohong Zhang^{3,*}

¹ School of Mathematics and Data Science, Shaanxi University of Science & Technology, Xi'an 710021, China; 221711032@sust.edu.cn

² School of Electrical and Control Engineering, Shaanxi University of Science & Technology, Xi'an 710021, China; bs1906001@sust.edu.cn

³ School of Mathematics and Data Science, Shaanxi University of Science & Technology, Xi'an 710021, China; zhangxiaohong@sust.edu.cn

* Correspondence: zhangxiaohong@sust.edu.cn; Tel.: 029-86168320

Abstract: In this paper, we mainly study neutrosophic overlap function and its induced residual implication. Firstly, we give the concept of neutrosophic overlap function and some examples which are introduced on the lattice. Secondly, the concept of representable neutrosophic overlap function and its related examples are given, meanwhile the general method of constructing representable neutrosophic overlap function by using intuitionistic overlap function is given. Finally, neutrosophic residual implication induced by representable neutrosophic overlap function and its basic properties are studied.

Keywords: neutrosophic overlap function; lattice; representable neutrosophic overlap function; neutrosophic residual implication

1. Introduction

In 1998, smarandache added an independent membership degree of uncertainty to intuitionistic fuzzy set in [1], thus putting forward the neutrosophic set for the first time. Neutrosophic Set is a powerful formal framework, which extends the concepts of classical set, fuzzy set, intuitionistic fuzzy set and interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy set from a philosophical point of view. Because intuitionistic fuzzy sets and interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets can only deal with incomplete information, but can't deal with uncertainty and inconsistent information that exists in reality. Therefore, neutrosophic set is introduced. Its uncertainty can be explicitly quantified, and its true membership, uncertain membership and false membership are expressed independent. However, its application is difficult to solve practical problems, so Wang et al. introduced the concept of single value middle wisdom set in [2], which is a specific instance of neutrosophic set. The relevant content of using single value neutrosophic set to solve decision-making problems is as follows [3-8].

Since the triangular norm has a wide range of applications in solving practical problems, it is also important to study the wide range of forms of the triangular norm in applications. The overlap function is a generalization of the continuous triangular norm[9]. Bustince et al. gave the definition of overlap function and grouping function in the following literature[10,11]. In recent years, overlap function and grouping function have been developed rapidly in theory and practice. See the following literature[12-16] for the rich achievements in the theoretical research of overlap function and grouping function. In decision problems, image processing and other fields of wide application

see the following literature[17-20]. In order to better deal with uncertain information, some scholars extend the overlap function [12, 21] to the intuitionistic fuzzy set, and introduce the method in [22].

In fuzzy logic, neutrosophic fuzzy sets are a generalization of zadeh fuzzy sets. Fuzzy implication and fuzzy residual implication play an important role in traditional fuzzy logic. Fuzzy implication [23] generalizes classical implication to fuzzy logic by considering truth values that vary in the unit interval $[0, 1]$ rather than in the set $\{0, 1\}$. Fuzzy implication is one of the important components of fuzzy logic, which plays a very important role in many fields, such as image processing, fuzzy control, data mining see the following literature [24-26], etc. Based on the wide application of fuzzy implication, it is necessary to study it from the theoretical point of view [19]. There are several different models of fuzzy implication such as R-implication induced by triangular norm[27], (S-N)-implication induced by triangular conorm and fuzzy negation [28], etc. Because overlap function is closely related to T-norm, based on the research of neutrosophic T-norm on neutrosophic fuzzy residual implication, and referring to the research of neutrosophic T-norm derived residual implication in Hu and Zhang [18], it is natural to consider the neutrosophic residual implication derived from neutrosophic overlap function.

The second section mainly introduces the basic knowledge that needs to be used, such as overlap function, grouping function, neutrosophic set and so on. In the third section, the new concept of neutrosophic overlap function and related examples are given. In addition, the concepts and examples of representable neutrosophic overlap function and non-representable neutrosophic overlap function are given respectively. Furthermore, the new concept of neutrosophic negation and De Morgan neutrosophic triple which can express the dual relationship between neutrosophic overlap function and neutrosophic grouping function, is given. The general method of constructing representable neutrosophic overlap functions by intuitionistic overlap functions is given. The fourth section focuses on neutrosophic residual implication induced by neutrosophic overlap function, and concludes that every neutrosophic residual implication induced by neutrosophic overlap function must be a neutrosophic implication. The last section summarizes the research content.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 ([29]) A binary function $O: [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called an overlap function if it satisfies the following conditions :

- (O1) $O(x, y) = O(y, x)$;
- (O2) $O(x, y) = 0$ if and only if $xy = 0$;
- (O3) $O(x, y) = 1$ if and only if $xy = 1$;
- (O4) $O(x, y) \leq O(x, z)$ if $y \leq z$;
- (O5) O is continuous.

Example 2.1 Some overlap functions are as follows, for all $x, y \in [0, 1]$,

$$(1) O_{\text{mm}}(x, y) = \min(x, y) \max(x^2, y^2);$$

$$(2) O_p(x, y) = x^p y^p, \text{ for } p > 0 \text{ and } p \neq 1;$$

$$(3) O_{\text{DB}}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \frac{2xy}{x+y}, & \text{if } x+y \neq 0, \\ 0, & \text{if } x+y = 0. \end{cases};$$

$$(4) O_{\text{min}}(x, y) = \min\{\sqrt{x}, \sqrt{y}\}.$$

Definition 2.2 ([30]) A binary function $G: [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a grouping function if it satisfies the following conditions :

- (G1) $G(x, y) = G(y, x)$;
- (G2) $G(x, y) = 0$ if and only if $x = y = 0$;
- (G3) $G(x, y) = 1$ if and only if $x = 1$ or $y = 1$;
- (G4) $G(x, y) \leq G(x, z)$ if $y \leq z$;
- (G5) G is continuous.

Example 2.2 Some grouping functions are as follows, for all $x, y \in [0, 1]$,

- (1) $G_{\text{mM}}(x, y) = 1 - \min(1 - x, 1 - y) \max((1 - x)^2, (1 - y)^2)$;
- (2) $G_p(x, y) = 1 - (1 - x)^p (1 - y)^p$, for $p > 0$ and $p \neq 1$;
- (3) $G_{\text{DB}}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \frac{x + y - 2xy}{2 - x - y}, & \text{if } x + y \neq 2, \\ 1, & \text{if } x + y = 2. \end{cases}$;
- (4) $G_{\text{min}}(x, y) = 1 - \min\{\sqrt{1 - x}, \sqrt{1 - y}\}$.

Definition 2.3 ([31]) An intuitionistic fuzzy set M in A is characterized by a membership function $\mu_M(x)$ and a non-membership function $\nu_M(x)$. A is a nonempty set. Then, an intuitionistic fuzzy set M can be denoted by

$$M = \{ (x, \mu_M(x), \nu_M(x)) \mid x \in A \} .$$

Where $\mu_M(x): A \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\nu_M(x): A \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with A the condition $0 \leq \mu_M(x) + \nu_M(x) \leq 1$, for all $x \in A$. And here $\mu_M(x), \nu_M(x) \in [0, 1]$ respectively denote the membership and the non-membership functions of the intuitionistic fuzzy set M .

Definition 2.4 ([2]) A single-valued neutrosophic set M in A is characterized by three functions: Truth-membership function $T_M(x)$, indeterminacy-membership function $I_M(x)$, and falsity-membership function $F_M(x)$. A is a nonempty set. Then, a single-valued neutrosophic set M can be denoted by

$$M = \{ \langle x, T_M(x), I_M(x), F_M(x) \rangle \mid x \in A \} .$$

Where $T_M(x), I_M(x), F_M(x) \in [0, 1]$ with the condition $0 \leq T_M(x) + I_M(x) + F_M(x) \leq 3$, for all $x \in A$.

Definition 2.5 ([32]) Let $(L; \leq_L)$ be a complete lattice. An overlap function on $(L; \leq_L)$ is a commutative, monotonicity, continuity mapping $O: L^2 \rightarrow L$, which satisfies $O(0_L, x) = 0_L$, for all $x \in L$; a grouping function on $(L; \leq_L)$ is a commutative, monotonicity, continuity mapping $G: L^2 \rightarrow L$, which satisfies $G(1_L, x) = 1_L$, for all $x \in L$.

Definition 2.6 ([18]) Now we consider the set D^* defined by,

$$D^* = \{ x = (x_1, x_2, x_3) \mid x_1, x_2, x_3 \in [0, 1] \} .$$

As defined above, if $x \in D^*$, then x has three components: The first component x_1 , the second component x_2 and the third component x_3 .

The order relation \leq_1 on D^* can also be defined by, for all $x, y \in D^*$,
 $x \leq_1 y$ if and only if $x_1 \leq y_1, x_2 \geq y_2, x_3 \geq y_3$.

Proposition 2.1 ([18]) $(D^*; \leq_1)$ is a partially ordered set.

Proposition 2.2 ([18]) $(D^*; \leq_1)$ is a complete lattice.

Definition 2.7 ([18]) The complement of x is defined by, for all $x \in D^*$,

$$x^c = (x_3, 1-x_2, x_1).$$

The maximum and minimum of $(D^*; \leq_1)$ are respectively denoted by $1_{D^*} = (1, 0, 0)$ and $0_{D^*} = (0, 1, 1)$.

3. Neutrosophic overlap function

This section gives the concept of neutrosophic overlap function and related examples, gives the concept and examples of representable and non-representable neutrosophic overlap function, and finally introduces a new method to construct representable neutrosophic overlap function through intuitionistic fuzzy overlap function.

Definition 3.1 A neutrosophic overlap function is a function $O: (D^*)^2 \rightarrow D^*$ that satisfies the following conditions, for all $x, u, y, v \in D^*$:

- (NO1) $O(x, y) = O(y, x)$;
- (NO2) $O(x, y) \leq_1 O(u, v)$ if $x \leq_1 u, y \leq_1 v$;
- (NO3) $O(0_{D^*}, y) = 0_{D^*}$ or $O(x, 0_{D^*}) = 0_{D^*}$;
- (NO4) $O(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$;
- (NO5) O is continuous.

Definition 3.2 A neutrosophic grouping function is a function $\Gamma: (D^*)^2 \rightarrow D^*$ that satisfies the following conditions, for all $x, u, y, v \in D^*$:

- (NG1) $\Gamma(x, y) = \Gamma(y, x)$;
- (NG2) $\Gamma(x, y) \leq_1 \Gamma(u, v)$ if $x \leq_1 u, y \leq_1 v$;
- (NG3) $\Gamma(1_{D^*}, y) = 1_{D^*}$ or $\Gamma(x, 1_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$;
- (NG4) $\Gamma(0_{D^*}, 0_{D^*}) = 0_{D^*}$;
- (NG5) Γ is continuous.

Example 3.1 Some neutrosophic overlap functions are as follows, for all $x, y \in D^*$:

- (1) $O_{mm}(x, y) = (O_{mm}(x_1, y_1), G_{mm}(x_2, y_2), G_{mm}(x_3, y_3))$
 $= (\min(x_1, y_1) \max(x_1^2, y_1^2), 1 - \min(1 - x_2, 1 - y_2) \max((1 - x_2)^2, (1 - y_2)^2), 1 - \min(1 - x_3, 1 - y_3) \max((1 - x_3)^2, (1 - y_3)^2))$;
- (2) $O_p(x, y) = (O_p(x_1, y_1), G_p(x_2, y_2), G_p(x_3, y_3)) = (x_1^p y_1^p, 1 - (1 - x_2)^p (1 - y_2)^p, 1 - (1 - x_3)^p (1 - y_3)^p)$, for
 $p > 0$ and $p \neq 1$;
- (3) $O_{DB}(x, y) = (O_{DB}(x_1, y_1), G_{DB}(x_2, y_2), G_{DB}(x_3, y_3)) = (\frac{2x_1 y_1}{x_1 + y_1}, \frac{x_2 + y_2 - 2x_2 y_2}{2 - x_2 - y_2}, \frac{x_3 + y_3 - 2x_3 y_3}{2 - x_3 - y_3})$, for
 $x_1 \neq y_1 \neq 0, x_2 \neq y_2 \neq 1$ and $x_3 \neq y_3 \neq 1$;
- (4) $O_{min}(x, y) = (O_{min}(x_1, y_1), G_{min}(x_2, y_2), G_{min}(x_3, y_3))$
 $= (\min\{\sqrt{x_1}, \sqrt{y_1}\}, 1 - \min\{\sqrt{1 - x_2}, \sqrt{1 - y_2}\}, 1 - \min\{\sqrt{1 - x_3}, \sqrt{1 - y_3}\})$.

Example 3.2 Some neutrosophic grouping functions are as follows, for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$(1) \quad G_{\text{mM}}(x, y) = (G_{\text{mM}}(x_1, y_1), O_{\text{mM}}(x_2, y_2), O_{\text{mM}}(x_3, y_3)) \\ = (1 - \min(1 - x_1, 1 - y_1) \max((1 - x_1)^2, (1 - y_1)^2), \min(x_2, y_2) \max(x_2^2, y_2^2), \min(x_3, y_3) \max(x_3^2, y_3^2));$$

$$(2) \quad G_p(x, y) = (G_p(x_1, y_1), O_p(x_2, y_2), O_p(x_3, y_3)) = (1 - (1 - x_1)^p (1 - y_1)^p, x_2^p y_2^p, x_3^p y_3^p), \text{ for } p > 0$$

and $p \neq 1$;

$$(3) \quad G_{\text{DB}}(x, y) = (G_{\text{DB}}(x_1, y_1), O_{\text{DB}}(x_2, y_2), O_{\text{DB}}(x_3, y_3)) = \left(\frac{x_1 + y_1 - 2x_1 y_1}{2 - x_1 - y_1}, \frac{2x_2 y_2}{x_2 + y_2}, \frac{2x_3 y_3}{x_3 + y_3}\right), \text{ for}$$

$x_1 \neq y_1 \neq 0, x_2 \neq y_2 \neq 1$ and $x_3 \neq y_3 \neq 1$;

$$(4) \quad G_{\text{min}}(x, y) = (G_{\text{min}}(x_1, y_1), O_{\text{min}}(x_2, y_2), O_{\text{min}}(x_3, y_3)) \\ = (1 - \min\{\sqrt{1 - x_1}, \sqrt{1 - y_1}\}, \min\{\sqrt{x_2}, \sqrt{y_2}\}, \min\{\sqrt{x_3}, \sqrt{y_3}\}).$$

Theorem 3.1 Let O be a binary operation on D^* , for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$O(x, y) = (O(x_1, y_1), G_1(x_2, y_2), G_2(x_3, y_3)).$$

Then O is a neutrosophic overlap function, where G_1, G_2 are grouping functions, O is an overlap function on $[0, 1]$.

Proof. For all $x, u, y, v \in D^*$, where $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3), y = (y_1, y_2, y_3), u = (u_1, u_2, u_3)$ and $v = (v_1, v_2, v_3)$.

(NO1) Let G_1, G_2 are grouping functions, O is an overlap function on $[0, 1]$. Since $O(x_1, y_1) = O(y_1, x_1), G_1(x_2, y_2) = G_1(y_2, x_2), G_2(x_3, y_3) = G_2(y_3, x_3)$, then $O(x, y) = O(y, x)$, for all $x, y \in D^*$.

(NO2) Let $x \leq_1 u$ and $y \leq_1 v$, then $O(x_1, y_1) \leq O(u_1, v_1), G_1(x_2, y_2) \geq G_1(u_2, v_2), G_2(x_3, y_3) \geq G_2(u_3, v_3)$.

Therefore, $O(x, y) \leq_1 O(u, v)$.

(NO3) $O(0_{D^*}, y) = (O(0, y_1), G_1(1, y_2), G_2(1, y_3)) = (0, 1, 1) = 0_{D^*}$, and $O(x, 0_{D^*}) = (O(x_1, 0), G_1(x_2, 1), G_2(x_3, 1)) = (0, 1, 1) = 0_{D^*}$.

(NO4) $O(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = (O(1, 1), G_1(0, 0), G_2(0, 0)) = (1, 0, 0) = 1_{D^*}$.

(NO5) Firstly, we prove left continuous. That's the proof $O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$. Because the overlap function and the grouping function are continuous, $O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i), G_1(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} G_1(x, y_i)$ and $G_2(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} G_2(x, y_i)$ is holding.

Then we have

$$O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = (O(x_1, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_{i1}), G_1(x_2, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_{i2}), G_2(x_3, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_{i3})) \\ = (\bigvee_{i \in I} O(x_1, y_{i1}), \bigvee_{i \in I} G_1(x_2, y_{i2}), \bigvee_{i \in I} G_2(x_3, y_{i3})) \\ = \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$$

Therefore the function O is left continuous.

Similarly, it is easy to show that $O(x, \bigwedge_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigwedge_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$, then the function O is right continuous. Hence the function O is continuous. To sum up, $O(x, y)$ is a neutrosophic overlap function.

Theorem 3.2 Let Γ be a binary operation on D^* , for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$G(x, y) = (G(x_1, y_1), O_1(x_2, y_2), O_2(x_3, y_3)).$$

Then Γ is a neutrosophic grouping function, where G is a grouping function, O_1 and O_2 are overlap functions on $[0, 1]$.

Proof. The proof is similar to the proof of **Theorem 3.1**.

Theorem 3.1 provides a way to construct neutrosophic overlap function using overlap functions and grouping functions which are defined on $[0, 1]$. But it requires a condition that $O = (O,$

G_1, G_2) holds. According to this condition, we introduce the concept of representable neutrosophic overlap function.

Definition 3.3 If and only if there exist G_1, G_2 are grouping functions, O is an overlap function on $[0, 1]$ satisfying for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$O(x, y) = (O(x_1, y_1), G_1(x_2, y_2), G_2(x_3, y_3)) .$$

Then the neutrosophic overlap function O is called representable.

Example 3.3 The representable neutrosophic overlap function is as follows, for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$O(x, y) = (O_{DB}(x_1, y_1), G_p(x_2, y_2), G_{mM}(x_3, y_3)) .$$

Proof. The first step is to prove that it is a neutrosophic overlap function. For all $x, u, y, v \in D^*$, where $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3), y = (y_1, y_2, y_3), u = (u_1, u_2, u_3)$ and $v = (v_1, v_2, v_3)$.

(NO1) Let $G_1 = G_p, G_2 = G_{mM} (p=2)$ are grouping functions, $O = O_{DB}$ is an overlap function on $[0, 1]$. Since $O_{DB}(x_1, y_1) = O_{DB}(y_1, x_1), G_p(x_2, y_2) = G_p(y_2, x_2), G_{mM}(x_3, y_3) = G_{mM}(x_3, y_3)$, then $O(x, y) = O(y, x)$.

(NO2) Let $x \leq_1 u$ and $y \leq_1 v$, then $O_{DB}(x_1, y_1) \leq O_{DB}(u_1, v_1), G_p(x_2, y_2) \geq G_p(u_2, v_2), G_{mM}(x_3, y_3) \geq G_{mM}(u_3, v_3)$. Therefore, $O(x, y) \leq_1 O(u, v)$.

(NO3) $O(0_{D^*}, y) = (O_{DB}(0, y_1), G_p(1, y_2), G_{mM}(1, y_3)) = (0, 1, 1) = 0_{D^*}$, and $O(x, 0_{D^*}) = (O_{DB}(x_1, 0), G_p(x_2, 1), G_{mM}(x_3, 1)) = (0, 1, 1) = 0_{D^*}$.

(NO4) $O(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = (O_{DB}(1, 1), G_p(0, 0), G_{mM}(0, 0)) = (1, 0, 0) = 1_{D^*}$.

(NO5) Firstly, we prove left continuous. That's the proof $O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$. Because the overlap function O_{DB} and the grouping functions G_p and G_{mM} are continuous, $O_{DB}(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} O_{DB}(x, y_i), G_p(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} G_p(x, y_i)$ and $G_{mM}(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} G_{mM}(x, y_i)$ is holding.

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) &= (O_{DB}(x_1, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_{i1}), G_p(x_2, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_{i2}), G_{mM}(x_3, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_{i3})) \\ &= (\bigvee_{i \in I} O_{DB}(x_1, y_{i1}), \bigvee_{i \in I} G_p(x_2, y_{i2}), \bigvee_{i \in I} G_{mM}(x_3, y_{i3})) \\ &= \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the function O is left continuous.

Similarly, it is easy to show that $O(x, \bigwedge_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigwedge_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$, then the function O is right continuous. Hence the function O is continuous. To sum up, $O(x, y)$ is a neutrosophic overlap function.

Finally, it is easy to see that satisfies $O(x, y) = (O(x_1, y_1), G_1(x_2, y_2), G_2(x_3, y_3))$, so it is a representable neutrosophic overlap function.

Definition 3.4 If and only if there exist G is a grouping function, O is an overlap function on $[0, 1]$ satisfying for any $x, y \in D^*$,

$$O(x, y) = (O(x_1, y_1), G(x_2, y_2), G(x_3, y_3)) .$$

Then the neutrosophic overlap function O is called standard representable.

Example 3.4 The standard representable neutrosophic overlap function is as follows, for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$O(x, y) = (O_{DB}(x_1, y_1), G_p(x_2, y_2), G_p(x_3, y_3)) .$$

Proof. The proof is similar to the proof of **Example 3.3**.

Definition 3.5 A N-dual representable neutrosophic overlap function O defined by, for any $x, y \in D^*$,

$$O(x, y) = (O(x_1, y_1), G(x_2, y_2), G(x_3, y_3)) .$$

And O and G are dual relations as follows,

$$O(x, y) = 1 - G(1 - x, 1 - y) .$$

Example 3.5 The N-dual representable neutrosophic overlap function is as follows, for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$O(x, y) = (O_p(x_1, y_1), G_p(x_2, y_2), G_p(x_3, y_3)).$$

Proof. The proof is similar to the proof of **Example 3.3**.

Definition 3.6 If and only if there exist a grouping function G and two overlap functions O_1, O_2 on $[0, 1]$ satisfying, for any $x, y \in D^*$,

$$G(x, y) = (G(x_1, y_1), O_1(x_2, y_2), O_2(x_3, y_3)).$$

Then the neutrosophic grouping function Γ is called representable.

Other concepts can be derived from the analogy of the neutrosophic overlap function.

In recent years, there have been many extensions of overlap functions. However, due to the limitations of existing definitions in solving practical problems with intuitionistic fuzzy information, scholars have proposed intuitionistic fuzzy overlap functions. In this paper, we further propose the representable neutrosophic overlap functions, and propose a general method to construct representable neutrosophic overlap functions from intuitionistic fuzzy overlap functions.

The following propositions present a method for constructing new representable neutrosophic overlap function (grouping function) with intuitionistic fuzzy overlap function (grouping function).

Proposition 3.1 Let $O(x, y)$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy overlap function: $O(x, y) = (O(x_1, y_1), G_2(x_3, y_3))$, for all $x = (x_1, x_3), y = (y_1, y_3) \in L$, where O is an overlap function, G_2 is a grouping function on $[0, 1]$, satisfying O and G_2 are dual to each other. Assume that G_1 is a grouping function on $[0, 1]$, satisfying

$$0 \leq O(x_1, y_1) + G_1(x_2, y_2) + G_2(x_3, y_3) \leq 3.$$

Then $O(x, y) = (O(x_1, y_1), G_1(x_2, y_2), G_2(x_3, y_3))$ is a representable neutrosophic overlap function, for any $x, y \in D^*$.

Proof. Refer to this literature [9], we can get $O(x, y) = (O_p(x_1, y_1), G_p(x_3, y_3))$, which is an intuitionistic fuzzy overlap function, then we add another grouping function $G_1 = G_{mM}$, satisfying $0 \leq O_p(x_1, y_1) + G_{mM}(x_2, y_2) + G_p(x_3, y_3) \leq 3$.

For all $x, u, y, v \in D^*$, where $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3), y = (y_1, y_2, y_3), u = (u_1, u_2, u_3)$ and $v = (v_1, v_2, v_3)$.

(NO1) Since $O_p(x_1, y_1) = O_p(y_1, x_1), G_p(x_3, y_3) = G_p(y_3, x_3), G_{mM}(x_2, y_2) = G_{mM}(x_2, y_2)$, then $O(x, y) = O(y, x)$.

(NO2) Let $x \leq_1 u$ and $y \leq_1 v$, then $O_p(x_1, y_1) \leq O_p(u_1, v_1), G_p(x_3, y_3) \geq G_p(u_3, v_3), G_{mM}(x_2, y_2) \geq G_{mM}(u_2, v_2)$. Therefore, $O(x, y) \leq_1 O(u, v)$.

(NO3) $O(0_{D^*}, y) = (O_p(0, y_1), G_{mM}(1, y_2), G_p(1, y_3)) = (0, 1, 1) = 0_{D^*}$, and $O(x, 0_{D^*}) = (O_p(x_1, 0), G_{mM}(x_2, 1), G_p(x_3, 1)) = (0, 1, 1) = 0_{D^*}$.

(NO4) $O(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = (O_p(1, 1), G_{mM}(0, 0), G_p(0, 0)) = (1, 0, 0) = 1_{D^*}$.

(NO5) Firstly, we prove left continuous. That's the proof $O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$. Because the overlap function O_p and the grouping functions G_p and G_{mM} are continuous, $O_p(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} O_p(x, y_i), G_p(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} G_p(x, y_i)$ and $G_{mM}(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} G_{mM}(x, y_i)$ is holding.

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) &= (O_p(x_1, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_{i1}), G_{mM}(x_2, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_{i2}), G_p(x_3, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_{i3})) \\ &= (\bigvee_{i \in I} O_p(x_1, y_{i1}), \bigvee_{i \in I} G_{mM}(x_2, y_{i2}), \bigvee_{i \in I} G_p(x_3, y_{i3})) \\ &= \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the function O is left continuous.

Similarly, we prove that $O(x, \bigwedge_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigwedge_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$, then the function O is right continuous. Hence the function O is continuous. To sum up, $O(x, y)$ is a neutrosophic overlap function.

And it is easy to see that satisfies $O(x, y) = (O(x_1, y_1), G_1(x_2, y_2), G_2(x_3, y_3))$, so it is a representable neutrosophic overlap function.

Proposition 3.2 Let $G(x, y)$ be a representable intuitionistic fuzzy grouping function: $G(x, y) = (G(x_1, y_1), O_2(x_3, y_3))$, for all $x = (x_1, x_3), y = (y_1, y_3) \in L$, where G is a grouping function, O_2 is an overlap function on $[0, 1]$. Suppose that O_1 is an overlap function on $[0, 1]$, satisfying,

$$0 \leq G(x_1, y_1) + O_1(x_2, y_2) + O_2(x_3, y_3) \leq 3.$$

Then $\Gamma(x, y) = (G(x_1, y_1), O_1(x_2, y_2), O_2(x_3, y_3))$ is a representable neutrosophic grouping function, for all $x, y \in D^*$.

Proof. The proof is similar to the proof of **Proposition 3.1**.

De Morgan triple describes the duality of fuzzy t-norm and fuzzy t-conorm with respect to fuzzy negator and is a perfect combination of fuzzy t-norm, fuzzy t-conorm and fuzzy negator. There are also corresponding studies on neutrosophic set. Based on the close connection between T norm and overlap function, it is natural to consider De Morgan neutrosophic triple about neutrosophic overlap function, neutrosophic grouping function and neutrosophic fuzzy negation. First, neutrosophic negation as an extension of fuzzy negation can be defined as follows.

Definition 3.7 ([18]) A neutrosophic negator is a function $N: D^* \rightarrow D^*$ that satisfies the following conditions:

- (NN1) $N(x) \geq_1 N(y)$, for all $x, y \in D^*$ such that $x \leq_1 y$;
- (NN2) $N(0_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$;
- (NN3) $N(1_{D^*}) = 0_{D^*}$.

If $N(N(x)) = x$, for all $x \in D^*$, then N is called an involutive neutrosophic negator.

The mapping $Ng: D^* \rightarrow D^*$ defined by, for all $(x_1, x_2, x_3) \in D^*$,

$$Ng(x_1, x_2, x_3) = (x_3, 1-x_2, x_1).$$

is an involutive neutrosophic negator. Then we call it the standard neutrosophic negator.

Definition 3.8 Let O be a neutrosophic overlap function, G be a neutrosophic grouping function, N be a neutrosophic negator.

The triple (O, N, Γ) satisfied the following conditions, for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$N(O(x, y)) = \Gamma(N(x), N(y));$$

$$N(\Gamma(x, y)) = O(N(x), N(y)).$$

is called a De Morgan neutrosophic triple. Moreover, O and Γ are dual with respect to N .

Theorem 3.3 Let N be an involutive neutrosophic negator.

(1) If Γ is a neutrosophic grouping function, the operator O defined by

$$O(x, y) = N(\Gamma(N(x), N(y))).$$

Then O is a neutrosophic overlap function. Moreover, (O, N, Γ) is a De Morgan neutrosophic triple.

(2) If O is a neutrosophic overlap function, the operator Γ defined by

$$\Gamma(x, y) = N(O(N(x), N(y)))$$

Then Γ is a neutrosophic grouping function. Moreover, (O, N, Γ) is a De Morgan neutrosophic triple.

Proof. (1) Let N be an involutive neutrosophic negator, Γ be a neutrosophic grouping function. For all $x, u, y, v \in D^*$, where $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3), y = (y_1, y_2, y_3), u = (u_1, u_2, u_3)$ and $v = (v_1, v_2, v_3)$.

(NO1) It is easy to prove that $O(x, y) = N(\Gamma(N(x), N(y))) = N(\Gamma(N(y), N(x))) = O(y, x)$.

(NO2) Let $x \leq_1 u$ and $y \leq_1 v$, $O(x, y) = N(\Gamma(N(x), N(y)))$, $O(u, v) = N(\Gamma(N(u), N(v)))$, because N is non-increasing, then $N(x) \geq_1 N(u)$, $N(y) \geq_1 N(v)$. Moreover $\Gamma(x, y) \leq_1 \Gamma(u, v)$ and if $x \leq_1 u, y \leq_1 v$, then $\Gamma(N(x), N(y)) \geq_1 \Gamma(N(u), N(v))$. Hence $N(\Gamma(N(x), N(y))) \leq_1 N(\Gamma(N(u), N(v)))$, then $O(x, y) \leq_1 O(u, v)$.

(NO3) $O(0_{D^*}, y) = N(\Gamma(N(0_{D^*}), N(y))) = N(\Gamma(1_{D^*}, N(y))) = N(1_{D^*}) = 0_{D^*}$, similarly $O(x, 0_{D^*}) = N(\Gamma(N(x), N(0_{D^*}))) = 0_{D^*}$.

(NO4) $O(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = N(\Gamma(N(1_{D^*}), N(1_{D^*}))) = N(\Gamma(0_{D^*}, 0_{D^*})) = N(0_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$.

(NO5) Firstly, we prove left continuous. That's the proof $O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$. As a result of $O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = N(\Gamma(N(x), N(\bigvee_{i \in I} y_i))) = N(\Gamma(N(x), \bigwedge_{i \in I} N(y_i))) = N(\bigwedge_{i \in I} \Gamma(N(x), N(y_i))) = \bigvee_{i \in I} N(\Gamma(N(x), N(y_i))) = \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$. Then we have $O(x, \bigwedge_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigwedge_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$. Therefore the function O is left continuous.

Similarly, we prove that $O(x, \bigwedge_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigwedge_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$, then the function O is right continuous. Hence the function O is continuous. To sum up, $O(x, y)$ is a neutrosophic overlap function.

Furthermore, (O, N, Γ) is a De Morgan neutrosophic triple.

(2) Similarly, assume that O is a neutrosophic overlap function, Γ can be proved to be a neutrosophic grouping function and (O, N, Γ) will be a De Morgan neutrosophic triple.

Example 3.6 some neutrosophic overlap functions and neutrosophic grouping functions are dual with respect to Ng.

- (1) $O_{mm}(x, y) = (O_{mm}(x_1, y_1), G_{mm}(x_2, y_2), G_{mm}(x_3, y_3))$ and $G_{mm}(x, y) = (G_{mm}(x_1, y_1), O_{mm}(x_2, y_2), O_{mm}(x_3, y_3))$;
In fact, $O_{mm}(N(x), N(y)) = O_{mm}((x_3, 1-x_2, x_1), (y_3, 1-y_2, y_1)) = (O_{mm}(x_3, y_3), G_{mm}(1-x_2, 1-y_2), G_{mm}(x_1, y_1))$, then $N(O_{mm}(N(x), N(y))) = N(O_{mm}(x_3, y_3), G_{mm}(1-x_2, 1-y_2), G_{mm}(x_1, y_1)) = (G_{mm}(x_1, y_1), 1-G_{mm}(1-x_2, 1-y_2), O_{mm}(x_3, y_3)) = (G_{mm}(x_1, y_1), O_{mm}(x_2, y_2), O_{mm}(x_3, y_3)) = \Gamma_{mm}(x, y)$. Thus, O_{mm} and Γ_{mm} are dual with respect to Ng.
- (2) $O_p(x, y) = (O_p(x_1, y_1), G_p(x_2, y_2), G_p(x_3, y_3))$ and $G_p(x, y) = (G_p(x_1, y_1), O_p(x_2, y_2), O_p(x_3, y_3))$;
- (3) $O_{DB}(x, y) = (O_{DB}(x_1, y_1), G_{DB}(x_2, y_2), G_{DB}(x_3, y_3))$ and $G_{DB}(x, y) = (G_{DB}(x_1, y_1), O_{DB}(x_2, y_2), O_{DB}(x_3, y_3))$;
- (4) $O_{min}(x, y) = (O_{min}(x_1, y_1), G_{min}(x_2, y_2), G_{min}(x_3, y_3))$ and $G_{min}(x, y) = (G_{min}(x_1, y_1), O_{min}(x_2, y_2), O_{min}(x_3, y_3))$;
- (5) $O(x, y) = (O_{DB}(x_1, y_1), G_p(x_2, y_2), G_p(x_3, y_3))$ and $G(x, y) = (G_p(x_1, y_1), O_p(x_2, y_2), O_{DB}(x_3, y_3))$.

We give the following theorem for non-representable neutrosophic overlap function.

Theorem 3.4 Let O be a binary function on D^* , for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$O(x, y) = \begin{cases} 0_{D^*}, & \text{if } x = 0_{D^*} \text{ or } y = 0_{D^*}, \\ 1_{D^*}, & \text{if } x = y = 1_{D^*}, \\ (x_1 y_1, x_3 y_3, x_3 y_3), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then O is a non-representable neutrosophic overlap function.

Proof. Firstly, we prove that O is a neutrosophic overlap function. For all $x, u, y, v \in D^*$, where $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$, $y = (y_1, y_2, y_3)$, $u = (u_1, u_2, u_3)$ and $v = (v_1, v_2, v_3)$.

- (NO1) It is easy to prove that $O(x, y) = O(y, x)$.
- (NO2) Let $x \leq_1 u$ and $y \leq_1 v$, then $O(x, y) \leq_1 O(u, v)$.
- (NO3) $O(0_{D^*}, y) = O(x, 0_{D^*}) = (0, 1, 1) = 0_{D^*}$.
- (NO4) $O(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = (1, 0, 0) = 1_{D^*}$.

(NO5) Firstly, we prove left continuous. That's the proof $O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$. As a result of $O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = (x_1 * \max(y_i), x_3 * \max(y_i), x_3 * \max(y_i)); \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i) = (x_1 * y_1, x_3 * y_1, x_3 * y_1) \vee (x_1 * y_2, x_3 * y_3, x_3 * y_3) \vee (x_1 * y_3, x_3 * y_3, x_3 * y_3) = (x_1 * \max(y_i), x_3 * \max(y_i), x_3 * \max(y_i))$. We have $O(x, \bigvee_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$. Therefore the function O is left continuous.

Similarly, we prove that $O(x, \bigwedge_{i \in I} y_i) = \bigwedge_{i \in I} O(x, y_i)$, then the function O is right continuous. Hence the function O is continuous. To sum up, $O(x, y)$ is a neutrosophic overlap function.

Secondly, for a representable neutrosophic overlap function O , there exists an overlap function O and two grouping functions G_1, G_2 on $[0, 1]$ such that $O(x, y) = (O(x_1, y_1), G_1(x_2, y_2), G_2(x_3, y_3))$.

Let $x = (0.3, 0.5, 0.6)$, $u = (0.3, 0.5, 0.2)$ and $y = (0.4, 0.5, 0.8)$. From $O(x, y) = (0.12, 0.48, 0.48)$ and $O(u, y) = (0.12, 0.16, 0.16)$. we get $G_1(x_2, y_2) = 0.48$ and $G_1(u_2, y_2) = 0.16$, so $G_1(u_2, y_2) \neq G_1(x_2, y_2)$. Hence $G_1(x, y)$ is not independent from x_3 , thus O is not representable.

In addition, the dual neutrosophic grouping function of O with respect to the standard neutrosophic negator Ng is G defined by, for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$G(x, y) = \begin{cases} 0_{D^*}, & \text{if } x = y = 0_{D^*}, \\ 1_{D^*}, & \text{if } x = 1_{D^*} \text{ or } y = 1_{D^*}, \\ (1 - (1 - x_1)(1 - y_1), 1 - (1 - x_3)(1 - y_3), 1 - (1 - x_3)(1 - y_3)), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then Γ is a non-representable neutrosophic grouping function.

4. Neutrosophic residual implication derived from neutrosophic overlap function

This section will introduce the notion of neutrosophic residual implication on the complete lattice D^* , investigate basic properties of neutrosophic residual implication. Firstly, we give the notion of neutrosophic implication on D^* .

Definition 4.1 ([18]) A neutrosophic implication is a function $I: (D^*)^2 \rightarrow D^*$ that satisfies the following conditions:

(NI1) I is non-increasing with respect to \leq_1 in its first variable, that is, $I(x, y) \geq_1 I(u, y)$, where $x, u, y \in D^*$ and $x \leq_1 u$;

(NI2) I is non-decreasing with respect to \leq_1 in its second variable, that is, $I(x, y) \leq_1 I(x, v)$, where $x, v, y \in D^*$ and $y \leq_1 v$;

(NI3) $I(0_{D^*}, 0_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$;

(NI4) $I(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$;

(NI5) $I(1_{D^*}, 0_{D^*}) = 0_{D^*}$.

Definition 4.2 There exists a neutrosophic overlap function O such that

$$I(x, y) = \sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, O(x, z) \leq_1 y\}.$$

Then the function $I: (D^*)^2 \rightarrow D^*$ is called a neutrosophic residual implication.

If I is a neutrosophic residual implication derived from a neutrosophic overlap function O , then it will be denoted by I_o .

In addition, a neutrosophic overlap function O satisfies the residual principle if and only if, for all $x, y, z \in D^*$:

$$O(x, z) \leq_1 y \text{ if and only if } z \leq_1 I_o(x, y).$$

Example 4.1 Give some examples of **Example 3.1** about neutrosophic residual implication derived from neutrosophic overlap function as follows, for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{O_{\text{max}}}(x, y) &= \begin{cases} (1, 0, 0), & \text{if } x_1 \leq y_1, x_2 \geq y_2 \text{ and } x_3 \geq y_3, \\ (1, \max\{1 - \sqrt{\frac{1-y_2}{1-x_2}}, 1 - \frac{1-y_2}{(1-x_2)^2}\}, \max\{1 - \sqrt{\frac{1-y_3}{1-x_3}}, 1 - \frac{1-y_3}{(1-x_3)^2}\}), & \text{if } x_1 \leq y_1, x_2 < y_2 \text{ and } x_3 < y_3, \\ (1, 0, \max\{1 - \sqrt{\frac{1-y_3}{1-x_3}}, 1 - \frac{1-y_3}{(1-x_3)^2}\}), & \text{if } x_1 \leq y_1, x_2 \geq y_2 \text{ and } x_3 < y_3, \\ (1, \max\{1 - \sqrt{\frac{1-y_2}{1-x_2}}, 1 - \frac{1-y_2}{(1-x_2)^2}\}, 0), & \text{if } x_1 \leq y_1, x_2 < y_2 \text{ and } x_3 \geq y_3, \\ (\min\{\sqrt{\frac{y_1}{x_1}}, \frac{y_1}{x_1^2}\}, \max\{1 - \sqrt{\frac{1-y_2}{1-x_2}}, 1 - \frac{1-y_2}{(1-x_2)^2}\}, \max\{1 - \sqrt{\frac{1-y_3}{1-x_3}}, 1 - \frac{1-y_3}{(1-x_3)^2}\}), & \text{if } x_1 > y_1, x_2 < y_2 \text{ and } x_3 < y_3, \\ (\min\{\sqrt{\frac{y_1}{x_1}}, \frac{y_1}{x_1^2}\}, 0, 0), & \text{if } x_1 > y_1, x_2 \geq y_2 \text{ and } x_3 \geq y_3, \\ (\min\{\sqrt{\frac{y_1}{x_1}}, \frac{y_1}{x_1^2}\}, \max\{1 - \sqrt{\frac{1-y_2}{1-x_2}}, 1 - \frac{1-y_2}{(1-x_2)^2}\}, 0), & \text{if } x_1 > y_1, x_2 < y_2 \text{ and } x_3 \geq y_3, \\ (\min\{\sqrt{\frac{y_1}{x_1}}, \frac{y_1}{x_1^2}\}, 0, \max\{1 - \sqrt{\frac{1-y_3}{1-x_3}}, 1 - \frac{1-y_3}{(1-x_3)^2}\}), & \text{if } x_1 > y_1, x_2 \geq y_2 \text{ and } x_3 < y_3. \end{cases} \\
 I_{O_{p=2}}(x, y) &= \begin{cases} (\frac{\sqrt{y_1}}{x_1}, 1 - \frac{\sqrt{1-y_2}}{1-x_2}, 1 - \frac{\sqrt{1-y_3}}{1-x_3}), & \text{if } x_1 > \sqrt{y_1}, x_2 < 1 - \sqrt{1-y_2} \text{ and } x_3 < 1 - \sqrt{1-y_3}, \\ (\frac{\sqrt{y_1}}{x_1}, 0, 0), & \text{if } x_1 > \sqrt{y_1}, x_2 \geq 1 - \sqrt{1-y_2} \text{ and } x_3 \geq 1 - \sqrt{1-y_3}, \\ (\frac{\sqrt{y_1}}{x_1}, 1 - \frac{\sqrt{1-y_2}}{1-x_2}, 0), & \text{if } x_1 > \sqrt{y_1}, x_2 < 1 - \sqrt{1-y_2} \text{ and } x_3 \geq 1 - \sqrt{1-y_3}, \\ (\frac{\sqrt{y_1}}{x_1}, 0, 1 - \frac{\sqrt{1-y_3}}{1-x_3}), & \text{if } x_1 > \sqrt{y_1}, x_2 \geq 1 - \sqrt{1-y_2} \text{ and } x_3 < 1 - \sqrt{1-y_3}, \\ (1, 1 - \frac{\sqrt{1-y_2}}{1-x_2}, 1 - \frac{\sqrt{1-y_3}}{1-x_3}), & \text{if } x_1 \leq \sqrt{y_1}, x_2 < 1 - \sqrt{1-y_2} \text{ and } x_3 < 1 - \sqrt{1-y_3}, \\ (1, 0, 0), & \text{if } x_1 \leq \sqrt{y_1}, x_2 \geq 1 - \sqrt{1-y_2} \text{ and } x_3 \geq 1 - \sqrt{1-y_3}, \\ (1, 0, 1 - \frac{\sqrt{1-y_3}}{1-x_3}), & \text{if } x_1 \leq \sqrt{y_1}, x_2 \geq 1 - \sqrt{1-y_2} \text{ and } x_3 < 1 - \sqrt{1-y_3}, \\ (1, 1 - \frac{\sqrt{1-y_2}}{1-x_2}, 0), & \text{if } x_1 \leq \sqrt{y_1}, x_2 < 1 - \sqrt{1-y_2} \text{ and } x_3 \geq 1 - \sqrt{1-y_3}. \end{cases} \\
 I_{O_{\text{min}}}(x, y) &= \begin{cases} (1, 0, 0), & \text{if } x_1 \leq y_1^2, x_2 \geq 1 - (1 - y_2)^2 \text{ and } x_3 \geq 1 - (1 - y_3)^2, \\ (1, 1 - (1 - y_2)^2, 0), & \text{if } x_1 \leq y_1^2, x_2 < 1 - (1 - y_2)^2 \text{ and } x_3 \geq 1 - (1 - y_3)^2, \\ (1, 0, 1 - (1 - y_3)^2), & \text{if } x_1 \leq y_1^2, x_2 \geq 1 - (1 - y_2)^2 \text{ and } x_3 < 1 - (1 - y_3)^2, \\ (1, 1 - (1 - y_2)^2, 1 - (1 - y_3)^2), & \text{if } x_1 \leq y_1^2, x_2 < 1 - (1 - y_2)^2 \text{ and } x_3 < 1 - (1 - y_3)^2, \\ (y_1^2, 0, 0), & \text{if } x_1 > y_1^2, x_2 \geq 1 - (1 - y_2)^2 \text{ and } x_3 \geq 1 - (1 - y_3)^2, \\ (y_1^2, 1 - (1 - y_2)^2, 0), & \text{if } x_1 > y_1^2, x_2 < 1 - (1 - y_2)^2 \text{ and } x_3 \geq 1 - (1 - y_3)^2, \\ (y_1^2, 0, 1 - (1 - y_3)^2), & \text{if } x_1 > y_1^2, x_2 \geq 1 - (1 - y_2)^2 \text{ and } x_3 < 1 - (1 - y_3)^2, \\ (y_1^2, 1 - (1 - y_2)^2, 1 - (1 - y_3)^2), & \text{if } x_1 > y_1^2, x_2 < 1 - (1 - y_2)^2 \text{ and } x_3 < 1 - (1 - y_3)^2. \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$I_{O_{DB}}(x, y) = \begin{cases} (\min\{1, \frac{x_1 y_1}{2x_1 - y_1}, \frac{2y_2 - x_2 y_2 - x_2}{1 - 2x_2 + y_2}, \frac{2y_3 - x_3 y_3 - x_3}{1 - 2x_3 + y_3}\}, & \text{if } x_1 > \frac{1}{2} y_1, x_2 < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_2 \text{ and } x_3 < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_3, \\ (\min\{1, \frac{x_1 y_1}{2x_1 - y_1}, 0, \frac{2y_3 - x_3 y_3 - x_3}{1 - 2x_3 + y_3}\}, & \text{if } x_1 > \frac{1}{2} y_1, 1 > x_2 \geq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_2 \text{ and } x_3 < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_3, \\ (\min\{1, \frac{x_1 y_1}{2x_1 - y_1}, \frac{2y_2 - x_2 y_2 - x_2}{1 - 2x_2 + y_2}, 0\}, & \text{if } x_1 > \frac{1}{2} y_1, x_2 < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_2 \text{ and } 1 > x_3 \geq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_3, \\ (\min\{1, \frac{x_1 y_1}{2x_1 - y_1}, 0, 0\}, & \text{if } x_1 > \frac{1}{2} y_1, 1 > x_2 \geq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_2 \text{ and } 1 > x_3 \geq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_3, \\ (1, \frac{2y_2 - x_2 y_2 - x_2}{1 - 2x_2 + y_2}, \frac{2y_3 - x_3 y_3 - x_3}{1 - 2x_3 + y_3}), & \text{if } 0 < x_1 \leq \frac{1}{2} y_1, x_2 < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_2 \text{ and } x_3 < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_3, \\ (1, 0, \frac{2y_3 - x_3 y_3 - x_3}{1 - 2x_3 + y_3}), & \text{if } 0 < x_1 \leq \frac{1}{2} y_1, 1 > x_2 \geq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_2 \text{ and } x_3 < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_3, \\ (1, \frac{2y_2 - x_2 y_2 - x_2}{1 - 2x_2 + y_2}, 0), & \text{if } 0 < x_1 \leq \frac{1}{2} y_1, x_2 < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_2 \text{ and } 1 > x_3 \geq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_3, \\ (1, 0, 0), & \text{if } 0 < x_1 \leq \frac{1}{2} y_1, 1 > x_2 \geq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_2 \text{ and } 1 > x_3 \geq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} y_3, \\ (0, 1, 1) & \text{if } x_1 = y_1 = 0, x_2 = y_2 = 1 \text{ and } x_3 = y_3 = 1. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 4.1 Let O be a neutrosophic overlap function on D^* , for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$I_O(x, y) = \sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, O(x, z) \leq_1 y\}.$$

Then $I_O(x, y)$ is a neutrosophic implication.

Proof. For all $x, u, y, v \in D^*$, where $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$, $y = (y_1, y_2, y_3)$, $u = (u_1, u_2, u_3)$ and $v = (v_1, v_2, v_3)$.

(NI1) Let $x \leq_1 u$ and since the non-decreasingness of O , $\{z \mid z \in D^*, O(x, z) \leq_1 y\} \supseteq \{z \mid z \in D^*, O(u, z) \leq_1 y\}$ then $\sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, z \leq_1 I_O(x, y)\} \geq \sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, z \leq_1 I_O(u, y)\}$. Thus $I_O(x, y) \geq_1 I_O(u, y)$. That is I_O is non-increasing with respect to \leq_1 in its first variable.

(NI2) Let $y \leq_1 v$ and since the non-decreasingness of O , $\{z \mid z \in D^*, O(x, z) \leq_1 y\} \subseteq \{z \mid z \in D^*, O(x, z) \leq_1 v\}$ then $\sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, z \leq_1 I_O(x, y)\} \leq \sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, z \leq_1 I_O(x, v)\}$. Thus $I_O(x, y) \leq_1 I_O(x, v)$. That is I_O is non-decreasing with respect to \leq_1 in its second variable.

(NI3) $I(0_{D^*}, 0_{D^*}) = \sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, O(0_{D^*}, z) \leq_1 0_{D^*}\} = 1_{D^*}$;

(NI4) $I(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = \sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, O(1_{D^*}, z) \leq_1 1_{D^*}\} = \sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, z \leq_1 1_{D^*}\} = 1_{D^*}$;

(NI5) $I(1_{D^*}, 0_{D^*}) = \sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, O(1_{D^*}, z) \leq_1 0_{D^*}\} = \sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, z \leq_1 0_{D^*}\} = 0_{D^*}$.

For neutrosophic residual implications, there are several important properties as follows.

Theorem 4.2 Suppose that O is a neutrosophic overlap function on D^* , I_O is a neutrosophic residual implication. Then, for all $x, y, z \in D^*$,

- (1) $I_O(0_{D^*}, y) = 1_{D^*}$;
- (2) $I_O(x, 1_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$;
- (3) $I_O(x, x) = 1_{D^*}$;
- (4) $I_O(1_{D^*}, y) = y$;
- (5) $I_O(x, y) \geq_1 y$;
- (6) $I_O(x, y) = 1_{D^*}$ if and only if $x \leq_1 y$;
- (7) $x \leq_1 I_O(y, z)$ if and only if $y \leq_1 I_O(x, z)$;
- (8) $x \leq_1 I_O(y, I_O(x, y))$.

Proof. For all $x, y, z \in D^*$, where $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$, $y = (y_1, y_2, y_3)$ and $z = (z_1, z_2, z_3)$.

(1) $I_O(0_{D^*}, y) = 1_{D^*}$ is the same thing as $I_O(0_{D^*}, y) = \sup\{z \mid z \in D^*, O(0_{D^*}, z) \leq_1 y\} = 1_{D^*}$, then $z = 1_{D^*}$ for $O(0_{D^*}, z) \leq_1 y$. Then this formula is proved.

The proofs of (2)–(4) is similar to the proof of (1).

(5) I is non-increasing with respect to \leq_1 in its first variable, then $I_O(x, y) \geq_1 I_O(1_{D^*}, y) = y$.

(6) $I_O(x, y) = 1_{D^*}$ if and only if $x \leq_1 y$. If $x \leq_1 y$, $O(1_{D^*}, x) \leq_1 y$, then $I_O(x, y) = 1_{D^*}$. On the contrary, if $I_O(x, y) = 1_{D^*}$, then $O(1_{D^*}, x) \leq_1 y$, thus $x \leq_1 y$.

(7) $x \leq_1 I_0(y, z)$ if and only if $y \leq_1 I_0(x, z)$. Since $x \leq_1 I_0(y, z)$, $O(y, x) \leq_1 z$. Thus, $y \leq_1 I_0(x, z)$. Likewise, $x \leq_1 I_0(y, z)$ can be proved from $y \leq_1 I_0(x, z)$.

(8) $x \leq_1 I_0(y, I_0(x, y))$. Since $O(y, x) \leq_1 O(x, y)$, then $x \leq_1 I_0(y, I_0(x, y))$.

Example 4.2 Some examples about neutrosophic residual implications derived from neutrosophic overlap functions were given by **Example 4.1**. And it is easy to verify that neutrosophic residual implication derived from neutrosophic overlap functions satisfy the properties described in **Theorem 4.2**.

Furthermore, for non-representable neutrosophic overlap function, take the neutrosophic overlap function O presented in **Theorem 3.4** for example, for all $x, y \in D^*$,

$$I_O(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1_{D^*}, & \text{if } x = 0_{D^*} \text{ or } y = 0_{D^*}; \text{ or } x = y = 1_{D^*}, \\ (1, [0, 1], \max\{\frac{y_3}{x_2}, \frac{y_3}{x_3}\}), & \text{if } x_1 \leq y_1, \\ (\frac{y_1}{x_1}, [0, 1], \max\{\frac{y_3}{x_2}, \frac{y_3}{x_3}\}), & \text{if } x_1 > y_1. \end{cases}$$

Then $I_0(x, y)$ is a neutrosophic implication and satisfies the properties given in **Theorem 4.2**.

5. Conclusions

As an important part of neutrosophic set theory, neutrosophic logic plays an significant role in it. Neutrosophic overlap function, neutrosophic grouping function and neutrosophic implication are very crucial neutrosophic logic operators. Under the first kind of inclusion relation, the definitions of neutrosophic overlap function and neutrosophic grouping function on complete lattice $(D^*; \leq_1)$ are defined and related examples are given. At the same time, new definitions of representable and non-representable neutrosophic overlap function are proposed. In the next place, based on the close relationship between overlap function and T-norm, a new definition of neutrosophic negation is given by analogy research, then the dual relationship between neutrosophic overlap function and neutrosophic grouping function on neutrosophic negation is described. Moreover, we show that definition of neutrosophic implication is given based on the complete lattice $(D^*; \leq_1)$ and the basic properties of neutrosophic residual implication are studied. Finally, the result that the residual implication derived from the neutrosophic overlap function must be neutrosophic implication is proved. Based on these results and some new results [33-42], we consider applying them to generalized neutrosophic overlap function and neutrosophic inference systems in the future.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Smarandache, F. *Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic Probability, Set, and Logic: Analytic Synthesis and Synthetic Analysis*; American Research Press: Santa Fe, NM, USA, 1998; pp. 25–38.
2. Wang, H.B.; Smarandache, F.; Zhang, Y.Q.; Sunderraman, R. Single valued neutrosophic sets. *Multispace Multistruct. Neutrosophic Transdiscipl.* **2010**, *4*, 410–413.
3. Tan, R.P.; Zhang, W.D. Decision-making method based on new entropy and refined single-valued neutrosophic sets and its application in typhoon disaster assessment. *Applied Intelligence*, **2021**, *51*, 283-307.
4. Stanujkic, D.; Karabasevic, D.; Popovic, G.; et al. Multiple-criteria decision-making based on the use of single-valued neutrosophic sets and similarity measures. *ECON COMPUT ECON CYB.* **2021**, *55*, 5-22.
5. Liu, P.D. The aggregation operators based on archimedean t-conorm and t-norm for single-valued neutrosophic numbers and their application to decision making. *Int. J. Fuzzy Syst.* **2016**, *18*, 849–863.

6. Ye, J. Multicriteria decision-making method using the correlation coefficient under single-valued neutrosophic environment. *Int. J. Gen. Syst.* **2013**, 42, 386–394.
7. Hu, Q.Q.; Zhang, X.H. New similarity measures of single-valued neutrosophic multisets based on the decomposition theorem and its application in medical diagnosis. *Symmetry* **2018**, 10, 466. DOI: 10.3390/sym10100466.
8. Wang, J.Q.; Zhang, X.H. Two types of single-valued neutrosophic covering rough sets and an application to decision making. *Symmetry* **2018**, 10, 710. Doi:10.3390/sym10120710.
9. Wen, X.F.; Zhang, X.H.; Lei, T. Intuitionistic Fuzzy (IF) Overlap Functions and IF-Rough Sets with Applications. *Symmetry* **2021**, 13, 1494. DOI: 10.3390/SYM13081494.
10. Bustince, H.; Fernandez, J.; Mesiar, R.; Montero, J.; Orduna, R. Overlap functions. *Nonlinear Anal.* **2010**, 72, 1488–1499.
11. Bustince, H.; Pagola, M.; Mesiar, R.; et al. Grouping, overlap, and generalized bientropic functions for fuzzy modeling of pairwise comparisons. *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems.* **2011**, 20, 405–415.
12. Dimuro, G.P.; Bedregal, B.; Bustince, H.; et al. On additive generators of overlap functions. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems.* **2016**, 287, 76–96.
13. Bedregal, B.; Dimuro, G.P.; Bustince, H.; et al. New results on overlap and grouping functions. *Information Sciences.* **2013**, 249: 148–170.
14. Qiao, J.S. On binary relations induced from overlap and grouping functions. *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* **2019**, 106, 155–171.
15. Qiao, J.S. On (IO, O)-fuzzy rough sets based on overlap functions. *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* **2021**, 132, 26–48.
16. Qiao, J.S. Overlap and grouping functions on complete lattices. *Inf. Sci.* **2021**, 542, 406–424.
17. Bustince, H.; Barrenechea, E.; Pagola, M. Image thresholding using restricted equivalence functions and maximizing the measures of similarity. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems.* **2007**, 158, 496–516.
18. Hu, Q.Q.; Zhang, X.H. Neutrosophic triangular norms and their derived residuated lattices. *Symmetry* **2019**, 11, 817. DOI: 10.3390/sym11060817.
19. Driankov, D.; Hellendoorn, H. Chaining of fuzzy if-then rules in Mamdani-controllers. *Proceedings of 1995 IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems.* **1995**, 1, 103–108.
20. Baczyński, M.; Jayaram, B. (S, N)-and R-implications: a state-of-the-art survey. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems.* **2008**, 159, 1836–1859.
21. Dimuro, G.P.; Bedregal, B. On residual implications derived from overlap functions. *Information Sciences.* **2015**, 312, 78–88.
22. De Miguel, L.; Gómez, D.; Rodríguez, J.T.; et al. General overlap functions. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, **2019**, 372, 81–96.
23. Baczynski, M.; Jayaram, B. *Fuzzy implications*. Studies in Fuzziness and Soft Computing, Springer, Berlin Heidelberg, 2008; pp. 151–160.
24. Zhang, F.X.; Liu, H.W. On a new class of implications: (g, u)-implications and the distributive equations. *International journal of approximate reasoning.* **2013**, 54, 1049–1065.
25. Klement, E.P.; Mesiar, R.; Pap, E. Triangular norms. Position paper I: Basic analytical and algebraic properties. *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* **2004**, 143, 5–26.
26. Vemuri, N.R. Mutually exchangeable fuzzy implications. *Information Sciences.* **2015**, 317, 1–24.
27. Baczyński, M.; Jayaram, B. (S, N)-and R-implications: a state-of-the-art survey. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems.* **2008**, 159, 1836–1859.
28. Baczyński, M.; Jayaram, B. On the characterizations of (S, N)-implications. *Fuzzy sets and systems.* **2007**, 158, 1713–1727.
29. Bustince, H.; Fernández, J.; Mesiar, R.; et al. Overlap index, overlap functions and migrativity. Proceedings of the Joint 2009 International Fuzzy Systems Association World Congress and 2009 European Society of Fuzzy Logic and Technology Conference, Lisbon, Portugal, July 20–24, 2009.
30. Bustince, H.; Pagola, M.; Mesiar, R.; et al. Grouping, overlap, and generalized bientropic functions for fuzzy modeling of pairwise comparisons. *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems*, **2011**, 20, 405–415.
31. Atanassov, K. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* **1986**, 20, 87–96.
32. Deschrijver, G. Implication functions in interval-valued fuzzy set theory. *Stud. Fuzziness Soft Comput.* **2013**, 300, 73–99.

33. Liang, R.; Zhang, X.H. Interval-valued pseudo overlap functions and application. *Axioms* **2022**, *11*, 216. DOI:10.3390/axioms11050216.
34. Jing, M.; Zhang, X.H. Pseudo-Quasi Overlap Functions and Related Fuzzy Inference Methods. *Axioms* **2023**, *12*, 217. DOI: 10.3390/axioms12020217.
35. Liang, R.; Zhang, X.H. Pseudo general overlap functions and weak inflationary pseudo BL-algebras. *Mathematics*. **2022**, *10*, 1396. DOI: 10.3390/math10091396.
36. Zhang, X.H.; Liang, R.; Bustince, H.; Bedregal, B.; Fernandez, J.; Li, M.Y.; Ou, Q.Q. Pseudo overlap functions, fuzzy implications and pseudo grouping functions with applications. *Axioms* **2022**, *11*, 593. DOI: 10.3390/axioms11110593.
37. Zhang, X.H.; Liang, R. Interval-valued general residuated lattice-ordered groupoids and expanded triangle algebras. *Axioms* **2023**, *12*, 42. DOI: 10.3390/axioms12010042
38. Zhang, X.H.; Sheng, N.; Borzooei, R.A. Partial residuated implications induced by partial triangular norms and partial residuated lattices. *Axioms* **2023**, *12*, 63. DOI: 10.3390/axioms12010063
39. Zhang, X.H.; Shang, J.Y.; Wang, J.Q. Multi-granulation fuzzy rough sets based on overlap functions with a new approach to MAGDM. *Information Sciences*. **2023**, *622*, 536-559.
40. Wang, J.Q.; Zhang, X.H.; Hu, Q.Q. Three-way fuzzy sets and their applications (II). *Axioms* **2022**, *11*, 532. DOI: 10.3390/axioms11100532
41. Hu, Q.Q.; Zhang, X.H. Three-way fuzzy sets and their applications (III). *Axioms* **2023**, *12*, 57. DOI: 10.3390/axioms12010057
42. Zhang, X.H.; Liang, R.; Bedregal, B. Weak inflationary BL-algebras and filters of inflationary (pseudo) general residuated lattices. *Mathematics*. **2022**, *10*, 3394. DOI: 10.3390/math10183394

Received: March 19, 2023. Accepted: July 20, 2023